

The relationship between homeopathy and the Dr Bach system of flower remedies: A critical appraisal

RA van Haselen^{1*}

¹Deputy Director of Research, The Royal London Homoeopathic Hospital NHS Trust, Great Ormond Street, London WC1N 3HR

The relationship between homeopathy and the Dr Bach system of flower remedies is explored. A historical perspective is given, doctrinal similarities and dissimilarities between both systems are discussed and the relationship between remedies used in homeopathy as well as in Dr Bach's system of flower remedies is explored. It is concluded that although both systems are clearly different, some common ground exists and that both systems may have a complementary role which is perhaps insufficiently recognised.

Keywords: Edward Bach; Bach flower remedies; Dr Bach system of flower and remedies; bowel nosodes

*'O great is the powerful grace that lies in herbs,
plants, stones and their true qualities'*

William Shakespeare (1564–1616) 'Romeo and Juliet', II

Introduction

Dr Bach system of flower remedies (DBS) was discovered in the 1930s by Dr Edward Bach.^{1,2} This discovery was the final stage in a successful career which had evolved from conventional medicine *via* bacteriology to homeopathy where he became widely respected for the discovery of the bowel nosodes, which are still used today. Following this recognition, he developed his own system of flower remedies, the best known of which is the Bach Flower Remedies. Although Dr Bach received continued support within the conventional world as well as from members of the homeopathic community at the time, many homeopaths rejected his work. Currently the situation is similar, although due to the growing popularity of DBS (currently used in 66 countries) interest within homeopathic circles has increased.

It is clear that DBS is a therapeutic system distinct from homeopathy. However, Dr Bach was greatly influenced by the ideas of Hahnemann and this is reflected in the philosophy and application of DBS. The current reality is that both systems are widely used and that homeopathic practitioners increasingly encounter patients who are using or have used Bach Flower Remedies or other DBS remedies. Also, some homeopaths use DBS in conjunction with homeopathy.^{3,4} Therefore it is important that homeopaths are, at least, informed about DBS. Even for the homeopath who is highly sceptical of DBS it is important to reflect on the origins of this scepticism in the light of a rational analysis. This article is an attempt to unravel and investigate the relationship between homeopathy and the remedies prepared in accordance with Dr Bach's methods.

Historical perspective

Dr Edward Bach (1886–1936) had a short but intense career in which he moved from orthodox medicine into homeopathy and finally into developing the Bach Flower Remedies in the 1930s. His life, like Hahnemann's, was dedicated to the high and only mission of the physician: 'to restore the sick to health, to cure'. Like Hahnemann, he was driven to innovation by

*Correspondence: Robbert A van Haselen, 60 Kew Road, Richmond, Surrey TW9 2PQ.

dissatisfaction with the limitations of conventional medicine. In an attempt to get closer to addressing the causes of illness, he pursued an interest in immunology and worked as an assistant bacteriologist at University College Hospital (London) from 1915–1918. This was at a time when immunology was rapidly evolving and one of the founders of modern immunology, Emil von Behring, recognised the close links of vaccinations to the principles of homeopathy.⁵ Bach's investigations focused on the role of the bacteriological content of the bowel in causing disease. In his view, non-lactose fermenting bacilli which were not directly pathogenic could lead to intestinal toxæmia and subsequently to chronic disease. Initially, he used hypodermic injections of vaccines made of these bacilli as a therapy.

From 1919 to 1922 Dr Bach was a pathologist and bacteriologist at the London Homoeopathic Hospital (now Royal London Homoeopathic Hospital). There, he read the work of Hahnemann and, like Emil von Behring, he was struck by the similarity between Hahnemann's discoveries and his own. Inspired by this, he successfully started to apply potentised vaccines orally rather than hypodermically,⁶ which ultimately led him to discover the seven Bach bowel nosodes still in use today. In the early 1920s his ideas on the relationship between vaccines and homeopathy were published in the *British Homoeopathic Journal*^{7–9} and by 1922 his growing fame brought him so much work that he decided to give up his post at the London Homoeopathic Hospital in order to set up a bigger laboratory. He also studied the effect of diet in combination with vaccine treatment.¹⁰ In 1925 he published a book on his work together with his co-worker C.E. Wheeler.¹¹ The book was widely welcomed by the medical profession, both allopathic and homeopathic.¹² In a lecture for the British Homoeopathic Society, Bach suggested that intestinal toxæmia was identical with Hahnemann's psora.¹³ This marked the highlight of his career in homeopathic circles. He acknowledged his work as a continuation of that of Hahnemann as leading the way to further discovery. By that time he was increasingly prescribing the bowel nosodes based on the mental/emotional constitutional picture of the patients rather than on bacteriological data, apparently with good results. In order to develop this method of prescribing, his co-worker Dr Dishington conducted homeopathic provings with the bowel nosodes.¹⁴

At this stage, the main innovation Bach pursued was replacing the bacterial nosodes with herbs. However, he indicated that the main stumbling block in this process was the observation that potencies of plant sources were of 'positive polarity', whereas bacterial nosodes were of 'negative polarity' (apparently essential for the effect of the nosodes). It is not exactly clear what he meant by polarity, but it was somehow related to the physico-chemical properties of homeopathic potencies.¹⁵ Also, he felt that the

bowel nosodes were limited because they addressed only one of the major miasms (psora). In the same year (1928) when he addressed the British Homoeopathic Society, he found the first three herbal remedies which would ultimately form the beginning of a series of the 38 DBS remedies. Initially, he potentised these remedies (*Impatiens*, *Mimulus* and *Clematis*) and prescribed them purely on the basis of the mental and emotional constitutional features of the patient. Encouraged by these results, he continued his search for more remedies and published his first observations in the '*Homoeopathic World*'.¹⁶

By spring 1930 he closed his microbiological laboratory and lucrative practice to dedicate himself completely to founding a new system of medicine. He went to Wales to find new remedies which is where he also discovered a new method of 'potentisation' involving placing the fresh flowers of plants in a bowl with spring water and exposing them to direct sunlight. He claimed that this method of preparing remedies overcame the problem of 'polarity' mentioned above.¹⁷ At a later stage, he additionally developed a second method of preparation (involving boiling) for the flowers and twigs of trees, bushes and plants most of which bloom early in the year before there is enough sunshine. The publication of further findings in '*The Homoeopathic World*' late 1930¹⁸ marked the definitive break between the new system of healing he propagated and homeopathy. He laid down his new philosophy of healing in the book '*Heal Thyself*' which was published in 1931.¹ Although he considered DBS a further advancement of the principles laid down by Hahnemann, his publication was not well received in homeopathic circles¹⁹ and deepened the rift between Bach and the homeopathic community. This did not deter him from continuing on the path he had taken and between 1930–1936 he discovered and refined in total 38 remedies. By the end of his life, he believed his work to be complete and that he had created a simple and accessible system of healing. He died in his sleep in November 1936.

Bach: a synopsis of his philosophy

Dr Bach based his work on a philosophy in which life is seen as a learning process and ill-health, whether mental or physical, is intended to help us understand more about ourselves and the purpose of our lives. According to Bach, health comes when we regain harmony between our physical and spiritual selves, leaving the body free to begin its own natural healing process. If mental/emotional equilibrium can be maintained, the body will remain in a state of health. This exclusive focus on the mental state of the sufferer is characteristic of Bach's approach: 'The individual is treated, and as he becomes well the disease goes'. In his book '*Heal Thyself*',¹ Bach describes his vision of the medicine of the future,

which he hopes will involve restoring peace, hope, joy and faith to suffering humanity.

Homeopathy and Dr Bach's system of flower remedies: doctrinal similarities and dissimilarities

It is clear that there is not one (type of) homeopathy: many different schools and types of approaches exist within homeopathy. Given the current state of evidence,²⁰ none of these approaches can be considered more or less valid than the other. The homeopathic 'point of reference' in the comparative analysis below is mainly classical Kentian homeopathy, unless otherwise stated.

The doctrinal similarities and dissimilarities between homeopathy and DBS are summarised in Table 1. Although the table is largely self explanatory, some further comments are given below.

Both are 'natural therapies' in the sense that they aim to mobilise and/or free the self healing energy in the patient. Hahnemann as well as Bach were both propagators of 'hippocratic medicine' in the sense that they believed in the role of a self regulating vital force, the 'vis medicatrix naturae' (= Hahnemann's dynamis), in regaining and maintaining health. They were both exponents of the empirical (rather than the rationalist) therapeutic method as eloquently described by Coulter²¹ in which symptoms are signs of the curative effort of the dynamis and must be interpreted as a positive or beneficial phenomena. In homeopathy as well as in DBS, treatment is based on treating the prevalent 'symptomatic layer'. This is

illustrated by the popular analogy in both systems which compares the progress of treatment with 'peeling the layers of the onion'. The principle that remedies are not to be repeated once improvement has taken place was inspired by Hahnemann and was also a key aspect of the use of the bowel nosodes.

The use of combinations of different remedies is widely promoted in DBS and this is clearly different from classical Kentian homeopathy. However, combination remedies are widely used in other schools of homeopathy. Also, it has recently emerged that even Hahnemann sometimes used 'remedies in tandem' during his later days in Paris,²² similar to the pluralist method currently widely employed in France.

Both systems use remedies of a non-material nature and in this sense both systems are equally controversial. Also, both systems aim to transfer the healing energy contained in the source material to a pharmaceutical medium and involve a form of 'energisation'. However, Bach claimed to have found a 'simple and more perfect' method of energisation of remedies which postulated that the healing energy of plants was concentrated in its flowers and that this healing energy could be passed onto a carrier (water) by the energy of the sun. According to this hypothesis, flower remedies come in only one strength. He additionally developed a second method which involved boiling the fresh flowers and twigs of trees, bushes and plants most of which bloom early in the year before there is enough sunshine.²³ Both methods of 'energisation' of the crude substances are clearly different from potentiation as used in homeopathy. By contrast, in homeopathy the exposure of remedies to direct sunlight or intense heat is thought to inactivate the

Table 1 Similarities and dissimilarities classical homeopathy and Bach's system of flower remedies (DBS)

DBS	Aspects in common	Classical homeopathy
	Treat the patient, not the disease	
	Remedies containing a non material healing energy	
	Prescribing based on presenting symptomatic layer	
	Mobilisation of self healing vital force	
	Symptoms are beneficial because they trigger the curative response of the organism	
	Curing from within out	
	Remedies not repeated once improvement takes place	
Use of combinations common/recommended	Use of single remedies	Use of combinations rare/exceptional
Mild, gentle system, <i>facilitating</i> healing response	Release of blocked energy	Deeply acting system, <i>provoking</i> healing response
Initial aggravations rare		Initial aggravations common
Sun and boiling method, <i>while</i> preparing tinctures	Herbal source material	Organic and inorganic sources
Verification in clinical practice in affected individuals	'Energisation' of the crude substances	Dilution and succussion, <i>after</i> preparation of tinctures
Possible mode of action: 'Harmony driving out wrong'	Empirical 'testing' of remedies	Proving on healthy volunteers and clinical verification
Simple, accessible healing system		Mode of action: 'similia similibus curentur'
Self-treatment intended by Bach		Sophisticated, complicated healing system
		Self-treatment not primarily intended

remedies. Interestingly, this implies that both systems postulate the influence of direct sunlight and intense heat on the energy contained in substances.

Although both systems aim to release blocked energy, DBS claims to be more gentle than homeopathy. Unlike homeopathy, strong initial aggravations are rarely reported in DBS. This may be related to Bach's assumption that, flower remedies aim to 'drive out wrong' with the harmonious energy of remedies that are 'life-giving and uplifting'. Homeopathic remedies are clearly presumed to act differently: remedies are given that temporarily intensify the illness and force the 'dynamis' to restore the disturbed balance. As mentioned above, Bach recognised the genius of Hahnemann, but claimed his new system was an advancement to Hahnemann's theories: 'The perfect method is not so much to repel the adverse influence, as to draw in its opposing virtue, and by means of this virtue flood out the fault; this is the law of opposites, of positive and negative'.¹⁶

Bach's aim was to develop a system which was simple and accessible in order to promote self help. By contrast, classical homeopathy is a very sophisticated system of healing which requires many years of study and is primarily aimed at use by trained professionals. In some ways Bach was ahead of his time by acknowledging the need for a simple, accessible form of medication for the purposes of self help: in recent times, a simple and more accessible form of homeopathy (involving either combination remedies or single remedies) as supplied to customers 'over the counter' (OTC) for self-treatment has become very popular.

A comparison of commonly used remedies

In Table 2 an overview is given of remedies commonly used in homeopathy as well as DBS. As a

'hypothesis generating exercise', reported mind symptoms of homeopathic remedies are tentatively compared with the indications for related DBS remedies. The number of mind symptoms for each of the remedies listed has been derived from the Complete Materia Medica Mind.²⁴ Recently, Dutch and German homeopathic doctors have taken up an interest in the use of 'tree remedies', including some trees also used in the DBS remedies. In Holland, homeopathic pathogenetic trials (provings) have taken place of beech, holly and oak but the results are not published yet (personal communication). In Germany, Marcus Jost published a homeopathic pathogenetic trial (proving) of oak²⁵ in which one of the emerging themes ('Struggling against untrue statements, without giving in') show some similarity with the use of oak as a DBS remedy ('Exhausted but struggles on'). These recent homeopathic pathogenetic trials may yield further information in the near future.

Table 2 indicates that in terms of its pharmaceutical source, Pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) comes closest to DBS because the young shoots together with the male and female flowers are used. Unfortunately, only a very limited number⁷ of characteristic mind symptoms are listed for *Pinus sylvestris*. In the other remedies listed, different parts and in some cases different varieties of the species are used in homeopathy. In spite of these differences, the mental and emotional symptoms of the remedies listed in Table 2 were tentatively analysed in order to explore the plausibility of any kind of relationship. The results of this analysis are given in Table 3. Table 3 shows that this analysis is almost exclusively limited to Aesculus and Clematis, which have at least some mental/emotional symptoms. Clematis, one of the first plants Bach explored, is of particular interest because he obtained his initial experiences with this remedy using homeopathic potencies of the tincture of the seed he had prepared in 1928.²⁶ Table 3 indicates that a number of the mental symptoms listed show similarity with the DBS

Table 2 Homeopathic remedies similar to those used in Dr Bach's system of flower remedies

Remedy	Common name	Part used in homeopathy	In materia medica*	In GHP (HAB) [#]	Mind symptoms [†] (N)
<i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i>	White chestnut (chestnut bud)	seed	A,B,C	yes	yes (79)
<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	Chichory	root	C	yes	no (0)
<i>Clematis erecta</i> [†]	Clematis	leaves, stems	A,B,C	yes	yes (182)
<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	Beech	nuts	C	no	yes (8)
<i>Ilex aquifolium</i>	Holly	leaves, berries, shoots	B,C	yes	no (2)
<i>Juglans regia</i>	Walnut	leaves, fresh fruit	A,B,C	no	yes (23)
<i>Ornithogalum umbellatum</i>	Star of Bethlehem	plant	B,C	no	yes (5)
<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	Pine	leaves, twigs	A,B,C	yes	yes (7)
<i>Populus tremuloides</i> [‡]	Aspen	bark	A,B,C	no	yes (6)
<i>Quercus robur</i>	Oak	fruits/acorns	C	yes	yes (3)
<i>Rosa canina</i>	Wild rose	fruits	C	no	no (0)
<i>Verbena hastata</i> [¶]	Vervain	plant	A,B,C	no	no (0) [‡]

*A = Allen, B = Boericke, C = Clarke; [#]German Homeopathic Pharmacopoeia (Homöopathisches Arzneibuch).

[†]Listed in the Complete Materia Medica Mind; N = Number of mind symptoms listed.

[‡]In therapy under Bach's system, the species *clematis vitalba* is used.

[¶]In therapy under Bach's system, the European aspen, *populus tremula* is used.

[¶]In Bach Therapy, the species *verbena officinalis* is used.

[‡]In the Complete Materia Medica Mind, one symptom is listed under *Verbena urticaefolia*.

Table 3 Homeopathic symptoms which show some similarity with the analogue *Bach Flower Remedies*

Remedy	Similar symptoms in the Complete Materia Medica Mind
<i>Aesculus</i> White chestnut * Unwanted thoughts * Mental arguments	Anxiety at night and on waking Concentration difficult: Fixing attention impossible While studying, reading Dullness, sluggishness, difficulty of thinking and comprehending Mental exertion aggravates Moral affections; antisocial†
Chestnut bud * Failure to learn from past mistakes	
<i>Clematis</i> * Dreaminess * Lack of interest in present	Absent-mindedness; Absorbed, buried in thought Aversion to company Concentration difficult; Confusion of mind Dullness, sluggishness, difficulty of thinking and comprehending Forgetfulness Deficiency of ideas Indifference, apathy Introspection; Meditation Slowness Increased mental strength Vanishing/loss of thoughts Moral affections; antisocial†
Holly * Hatred, envy, jealousy	

*Keywords of the *Bach Flower Remedies*; for more detailed information, see the literature.

†Rubric directly referred to Bach in the Complete Materia Medica Mind.

Clematis features (Insufficient interest in present circumstances: dreamy, drowsy, not fully awake, no great interest in life). A *clematis* symptom that seems different from the others is 'increased mental strength' and is derived from a homeopathic pathogenetic trial (proving) reported by Allen²⁷ where it is described by three subjects as 'Power of thinking and desire for mental work increased, and accompanied by general well feeling; this condition, however, lasted only half an hour after which there was disinclination for mental work, with mental exhaustion', 'Continued desire for mental work, for several days after the proving', 'increased mental activity during the first five days, followed on the sixth day by ill-humour and sleepiness'. As described by Hahnemann in his *Organon*,²⁸ the symptom of 'increased mental strength' seems to refer to the *primary action* of *Clematis* on a sensitive individual, whereas the opposite symptoms of mental exhaustion, vanishing/loss of thoughts, etc. seem to refer to the *secondary action*. As mentioned above, Bach claimed to heal by drawing in the opposing virtue, and by means of this virtue 'flood out' the fault. In accordance with this hypothesis, 'increased mental strength' could well be the 'virtue' (primary action) associated with *clematis* and by using and preparing the flowers, these primary actions are brought out further. It should be emphasised again that this explanation is a merely a hypothesis suggesting that the presence of a 'healing

concept' underlying homeopathy as well as DBS is not completely implausible.

Discussion

Hahnemann and Bach were both inspired by strong inner convictions in their discoveries. Although without a considerable amount of zeal they probably would not have been able to overcome resistance, it also alienated them in some ways. In Bach's case, resistance was created by his view that disease was always a 'correction' for an error. Although most people would agree that emphasising the role of personal responsibility in regaining and/or maintaining health is very important, not everybody will agree with Bach's total emphasis on this principle. Also, not everybody agreed with his (utopian) vision that in the future people will be ashamed of being ill,²⁹ and some homoeopaths at the time¹⁹ thought he negated the fact that many people who have led an exemplary life from a spiritual point of view, still develop physical illnesses.

Apart from these more philosophical objections, it was understandable that DBS was not well received in homeopathic circles. However, Hahnemann was not accepted by his contemporaries mainly because he had different, innovative ideas and many historical examples can be given: Jenner, the originator of vaccination, had against him the full weight of the Royal College of Physicians. Semmelweis, who identified the cause of puerperal fever as being due to an invasion of 'inflammatory irritants' (bacteria had not been discovered at that time) was laughed at, or at best ignored by his colleagues. Therefore, care should be taken in making judgements of a system, simply because it is different and not, as yet, explicable.

Like Hahnemann, Bach was ahead of his time: for instance his emphasis on the importance of the bacterial flora in maintaining health, the anticipation of the need for a simple accessible system of natural healing which can be used over-the-counter (OTC) for self help and, like Hahnemann, his emphasis on the importance of compassion as part of the healing process.

A serious constraint surrounding the further dissemination of DBS remedies within medical circles is the presence of a 'credibility gap'. In DBS as well as in homeopathy the mode of action is unknown, but for the latter a fair amount of evidence has been accumulated supporting the notion that homeopathic remedies are more than placebos.²⁰ For DBS, the evidence base is much weaker. Rühle conducted a pilot trial in the clinical domain of obstetrics³⁰ and one placebo controlled study was conducted in the US with healthy volunteers.³¹ In spite of claiming positive trends, the quality of both trials is poor and numbers of subjects low. Therefore no conclusions are warranted on the basis of these trials. A placebo controlled trial with students (examination anxiety) is currently being

completed in the UK,³² but no results had been published when this paper was submitted. Apart from this, one observational study involving the treatment of 115 patients in the context of psychological counselling could be identified.³³ In conclusion, the evidence base of DBS is currently still almost exclusively based on anecdotal data which means the 'credibility gap' is even greater than for homeopathy.

The comparison between remedies used both in homeopathy as well as DBS, is complicated by the fact that these homeopathic remedies are not polychrests and little is known about the mental/emotional picture. This also means the comparison is solely based on data from homeopathic pathogenetic trials (provings) which complicates matters further because problems with the validity of such data have been reported.³⁴ Therefore, as mentioned above, these data should be interpreted tentatively and with caution.

Conclusion

This article has illustrated that although homeopathy and DBS are clearly different, relationships between both systems exist. Moreover, homeopaths increasingly claim that homeopathy and DBS can complement each other: flower remedies can be used when the condition of the patient is weakened to such an extent that severe aggravations of homeopathic remedies are feared; or when there is concern that the use of conventional drugs, coffee, etc. may antidote homeopathic remedies. Furthermore, it is claimed that DBS remedies which have been previously applied with success, can be pointers in the direction of specific homeopathic remedies.⁴ Also, it has been suggested that flower remedies can be used to 'open up' a case:³ by stimulating the vital force, a clearer homeopathic symptom picture can emerge and the potential to respond to homeopathic remedies is increased. For a fuller discussion about DBS and homeopathy, also see the article by Franz.³⁵ This article was published in a leading German homeopathic journal because the editorial board felt that homeopathic doctors should be informed about the topic. The homeopathic remedies related in their mental/emotional aspects to the different DBS remedies are listed in the appendix⁴ (with permission from the author). For a repertory of DBS remedies similar to the mind section of Kent's Repertory, see the publication by Richardson-Boedler.³

Overall it can be concluded that although both systems are clearly different, some common ground exists. Moreover, both systems may have a complementary role which is perhaps insufficiently recognised.

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Trademark notice

Bach Flower Remedies[®] is a trade mark of Bach Flower Remedies Limited, Oxon, England. Other ranges of remedies said to be made in accordance with Dr Bach's system of flower remedies are also available.

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Appendix

The 38 Bach Flower Remedies and their related homeopathic remedies (Reprinted with permission).

Bach Flower Remedy

Homoeopathic remedies related at mental and/or emotional level

<i>Agrimony</i>	Agar., Ars., Coff., Croc., Fl-ac., Lyc., Mag-m., Nux v., Phos., Tub.
<i>Aspen</i>	Acon., Ars., Bell., Cann-i., Kali-c., Phos., Op., Sep., Verat., Stram.
<i>Beech</i>	Calc-p., Hyos., Lyc., Nat-m, Pall., Plat., Sep., Verat.
<i>Centaury</i>	Coff., Puls.
<i>Cerato</i>	Ant-c., Graph., Hel., Nat-m., Puls., Thuja.
<i>Cherry plum</i>	Bell., Calc., Cench., Hyos., Lach., Manc., Puls., Stram.
<i>Chestnut bud</i>	<i>Repressed sexual drive</i> : Bufo, Canth., Lach., Mur., Orig., Phos., Plat., Staph., Tarent.
<i>Chicory</i>	Agar., Bar-c., Calc., Cedr., Chin., Lach., Nat-m., Nit-ac.
<i>Clematis</i>	Ars., Dulc., Ign., Lil-t., Mosch., Nat-m, Pall., Plat., Sep.
<i>Crab apple</i>	Asar., Cann-i., Cann-s., Kali-br., Nat-m., Tub.
<i>Elm</i>	Ars., Lyc., Nat-m, Staph., Sulph., Syph.
<i>Gentian</i>	<i>Drainage remedies</i> : Berberis, Card-m., Chel., Sol-v.
<i>Gorse</i>	<i>Sycotic remedies</i> : Med., Puls., Thuja
<i>Heather</i>	Arg-n., Calc., Sil.
<i>Holly</i>	Ambr., Chel., Dulc., Nat-m, Psor., Thuja, Staph.
<i>Honeysuckle</i>	Acon., Agn., Ars., Calc., Carb-v., Nit-ac.
<i>Hornbeam</i>	Lach., Merc., Nat-m., Pall., Par., Phos., Stram., Sulph., Syph.
<i>Impatiens</i>	Hep., Hyos., Lach., Nat-m., Nit-ac., Pall., Stram., Tub.
<i>Larch</i>	Caps., Carb-an., Cimic., Phos.
<i>Mimulus</i>	<i>Complementary remedies</i> : Ars., Aur., Caust., Coff.
<i>Mustard</i>	Agar., Arg-n., Ph-ac., Phos., Psor., Sil.
<i>Oak</i>	Cham., Coff., Lach., Lyc., Nux-v., Tarent.
<i>Olive</i>	Anac., Arg-n., Aur., Calc., Lyc., Plat., Sil.
<i>Pine</i>	Ars., Calc., Caust., Cham., Fl-ac., Lyc., Nat-m., Nit-ac., Phos.
<i>Red Chestnut</i>	Alum., Aur., Cann-i., Cann-s., Cimic., Graph., Med., Valer.
<i>Rock rose</i>	Aur., Nux-v., Plb., Tarent.
<i>Rock Water</i>	Abrot., Alum., Ars., Carb-v., Chin., Helon., Mur-ac., Stann.
<i>Scleranthus</i>	Ars., Aur., Hell., Ign., Kali-br., Lach., Lil-t., Nat-m., Verat.
<i>Star of Bethlehem</i>	Aeth., Ars., Bar-c., Caust., Dulc., Phos., Puls., Sulph.
<i>Sweet Chestnut</i>	Acon., Arn., Ars., Op.
<i>Vervain</i>	Cann-i., Hyos., Lyc., Myric., Puls., Sep., Sulph., Stram., Thuja
<i>Vine</i>	Anac., Croc., Kal-bi., Med., Merc., Nat-m., Puls., Tub.
<i>Walnut</i>	Ign., Nat-m., Op., Ph-ac., Puls., Sep., Staph.
<i>Water violet</i>	Ars., Aur., Calc., Psor.
<i>White Chestnut</i>	Ars., Caust., Lach., Nat-m, Rob., Sel., Sulph., Thuju.
<i>Wild Oat</i>	Abrot., Anac., Chel., Dulc., Hep., Kali-p., Lyc.
<i>Wild Rose</i>	<i>Attack</i> : Bell., Bufo, Hyos., Tarent.
<i>Willow</i>	<i>Violent</i> : Bell., Hyos., Stram.
	Calc., Graph., Nux-v., Puls.
	Aeth., Ars., Bry., Gels., Nat-m.
	Arg-nit., Ambr.
	Cham., Coff., Ign., Kali-c., Sulph., Stann., Tub.
	Agn., Ars., Calc-p., Carb-v., Chin., Ign., Mur-ac., Nit-ac., Phos-ac., Pic-ac., Stann.
	Caps., Ign., Lach., Lil-t., Lyc., Mag-m., Nat-m., Nit-ac.